

A Study on Consumer Behavior towards Fast Moving Consumer Goods at Tirupur Town

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: August

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Vasuki, R. "A Study on Consumer Behavior towards Fast Moving Consumer Goods at Tirupur Town." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 153-63.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451677>

Dr. R. Vasuki

HOD, Department of commerce

KSR College of Arts & Science for Women, Tiruchengodu

Abstract

Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) division is the fourth biggest segment in India touching everyone's life consistently. With changing profile and outlook of Indian customers, this segment has a productive potential as semi-urban, urban ghettos and developing country portion. In coming years, with quickly changing socio – financial scene, base of pyramid will be the quickest developing customer market. The exploration work is a try to concentrate on the components that influence the purchasing conduct of customers living in unapproved settlements in urban India. The study was directed with the assistance of semi organized poll utilizing blended technique research approach utilizing illustrative configuration with simultaneous planning. The concentrate initially inspected the socio – monetary components, trailed by item inclinations – bland or marked under different heads of FMCG item classifications, explanations behind such inclinations took after by variables influencing the purchasing conduct. There were twenty one such components put under five general classes. The discoveries of the study uncover those customers in such ranges lean toward brands over nonexclusive items. In the meantime unwavering quality, item highlights and financial elements largely affect purchasing conduct alongside limited time offers.

Keywords: Buying Behavior, FMCG, Unauthorized Colonies, Brand Preferences, Consumer Decision Making.

Introduction

Goods (FMCG) frame a noteworthy part of procurement for purchasers on the loose. The segment has been developing at a CAGR of 11% in the course of the last decade, (Report: The Indian FMCG Industry, 2012). A well determined appropriation system and skillful worth chain, and in addition extraordinary rivalry between the composed and disorderly division (Report, FMCG Industry in India) are the signs of this sector.

Consumer behavior

Consumer behavior is defined as activities people undertake when obtaining, consuming, and disposing of products and services (et al Blackwell, 2001). The study of consumer behavior does not only include reasons for buying but also the consumption process of the consumer at large. In the entire process of buying, consumers get driven by influences such as feelings, motivation, income, lifestyle, opinions, culture, personality etc.

Objectives of Study

1. To identify their level of satisfaction in purchase of various FMCG products.
2. To find out the brand preference of FMCG consumers.
3. To determine the various factors influencing the behavior of FMCG consumer

Statement of the Problem

Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG), are items that are sold rapidly at generally ease. The benefit from these items is moderately little and the offering is in huge amounts, so the combined benefit on such items can be extensive. The preparations of Fast Moving Consumer Goods organizations have huge rivalry and they are compelled to discover better approaches for profiting. They did this by taking in the shopper regular needs and purchasing intentions, and to building up the arrangement. This is exceptionally troublesome due to the purchasers has diverse requirements, distinctive desires furthermore an ocean changes in the way of life and ways of life. At present the shoppers are more dynamic, their taste, inclinations are additionally evolving. The purchasers are likewise looking item separation and the accommodation advertised. The shopper has certain desire from marked things as far as its quality, cost and bundling. The cash spent on notice makes the customer mindful of the most recent brands in the business sector. The business sectors conditions in don't accept a composed working example. The status of showcasing should be comprehended in perspective of social elements and different monetary and operational crevice hypotheses. In this way, suitable getting ready for business sector as far as exchange for channel base, innovation and behavioral measurements needs more noteworthy accentuation for accomplishing better financial proficiency. The shoppers are finding different issues in selecting their quick moving buyer products. All together satisfy their desire to know the customer conduct in the buy choice in the FMCGs items. In this setting it is distinguished that there is a requirement for examination work in the field of shopper conduct of FMCG in the Tirupur.

Research Design and Methodology

Research Design

Descriptive Research Design

Descriptive Research Design is used for formulating a problem for more precise investigation from an operation point of view.

Sample Design

A Sample Design is a definite plan for obtaining the sample from the given population.

A. Population

All the respondents on various department stores in Tirupur city

B. Sampling Unit

The elementary units or the groups or cluster of such units may form the basis of sampling process. Sampling unit may be geographical or social unit. The sampling units taken for this study are from Tirupur.

C. Sampling Size

This refers to the number of items to be selected from the universe to constitute a sample. In this study 125 respondents in various department stores in Tirupur taken as a sample for the study.

Statistical Tools

1. Percentage analysis
2. Chi-Square
3. Garrett ranking technique

4. Factor analysis
5. ANOVA

Review of related Research

AnkitKatiyar, and NikhaKatiyar, (2014) “An Empirical Study of Indian Consumer Buying Behavior of FMCG Products (With Special Reference Of Bathing Soap)”, washing cleanser are quick moving purchaser merchandise that have seen a surge in their deals in the previous couple of decades in India more individuals are opening up to testing and experimenting with more up to date shower cleanser. This study is endeavor to cover the different components that impact the purchasing choice of customers who plan to buy as well as utilized shower cleanser. FMCG area is the fourth biggest part in India touching everyone life is in consistently. The FMCG merchandise segment is imperative patron to India as gross residential items.

Chitra. R (2014) “An experimental study on Customers Purchase Intention towards Branded Apparels”, this paper expects to study variables influencing customers buy expectation towards marked clothing. Buy expectation is clarified as far as general customer variables (regulating impact, buyer certainty) and brand particular variables (saw quality, passionate worth).

Nasrudeen .R and Mohamed, (2014) “Level of Consumption of Fast Moving Consumer Goods by Rural Consumers – An Analytical Study”, as far back as freedom of India, on account of some undeniable reasons, showcasing procured a to a great extent urban inclination. It was the green insurgency in the seventies which gave a truly necessary help to agribusiness based provincial economy in the nation. Along these lines, numerous organizations began indicating enthusiasm for the rustic markets and extend their entrance to achieve littler town and towns. Further, now-a-days provincial buyers are acting like urban shoppers towards the urban way of life, style, taste, inclinations, and so on.

Rajasekaran, B and Saravanan, P. A. (2014) highlighted, “Buyer Satisfaction on Fast Moving Consumer Goods”. The study tosses on the states of mind, qualities, convictions and impression of the customers as to the utilization of quick moving shopper products.

Shanmugapriya .G and Sethuraman .R, (2014) “Consumers Satisfaction towards Hamam Soap in Thanjavur Town”, the showcasing situation in India has experienced tremendous change since 1991 because of the monetary changes. Post-progression, rivalry heightened in each product offering and market, which constrained brands to rethink their standards of presence in all ventures. In the FMCG business, particularly in can cleanser segment there has been extreme rivalry among the MNCs, national and nearby players. Brand unwaveringness is controlled by a few unmistakable mental procedures of the purchasers and involves multivariate estimations.

Sonia and Garima Dalal, (2014) “To Study the Satisfaction Level of Customers towards the Brand of Consumer’s Goods - A Study Carried out on Rural Masses”, The Indian Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) industry started to shape amid the last fifty odd years. The FMCG division is a foundation of the Indian economy. This segment touches each part of human life. Indian FMCG market has been partitioned for quite a while between the sorted out area and the sloppy division.

C. Muthuvelayutham (2012) in his study titled “The Study of Consumer Brand Loyalty on FMCG-Cosmetic Products with Special Reference to Madurai” breaks down the relationship between demographic variables on the brand faithfulness of the shoppers and tries to distinguish the purchaser’s exchanging elements in regarded chose item class. This study is basically a connection study. An arbitrarily chose test of 600 from Tamil Nadu State, South India, especially Madurai, Tuticorin, Kanyakumari areas were chosen to break down. To demonstrate the measure of relationship between’s the variables, Chi-square test was utilized as a part of this study. Comes

about demonstrate that among the variables age, instruction level and sexual orientation have the most huge effect on purchaser’s image unwaveringness.

B.V.N.G. Chandrasekhar (2012) in his study “Customer Buying Behavior and Brand Loyalty in Rural Markets: FMCG”, intends to study brand steadfastness of different brands in rustic markets and recognize the nearness and the significance of neighborhood brands. The primary information was gathered through a poll. This study was led on an example of 60 respondents in the town’s satanapalli, tadipattri and mallapur.

GihanWijesundera (2010) in this article “Elements affecting the interest of magnificence cleanser among female shoppers in the more noteworthy Colombo area” Purpose of this study is to investigate how the showcasing blend and demographical variables impact the brand inclination and acquiring conduct of excellence cleanser among the female customers in the more prominent Colombo locale. The outcomes demonstrated that there were measurable connections between value, item, instruction, occupation and band inclination and there was no factual relationship between spot, advancement, age, wage level, conjugal status, skin sort, social variables, and substitute item with the brand inclination.

In this manner the examination reasons that the value, item, training and occupation are just having a measurable association with the brand inclination of female buyers in the more prominent Colombo locale.

NuntasareeSukat (2009) in this article “A model of male purchaser conduct in purchasing healthy skin items in Thailand” The study motivation behind the examination was assessed in some profundity the wonders of male buyer conduct in purchasing skin health management items in Thailand. Keeping in mind the end goal to adapt to the examination reason, Fishbone and Janzen’s hypothesis of contemplated activity model is utilized as a hypothetical structure and altered by including the mental self portrait build. The examination goal was discover the “To what degree do convictions in item trait, mental self portrait, Normative impacts, and states of mind toward applying healthy skin items, influence Thai male buyers’ buy aim and buy conduct in purchasing skin health management items. The scientist was discover the outcome or affirm that convictions, mental self view, regularizing impacts, and demeanors have sways on buy expectation and buy conduct in purchasing healthy skin items among Bangkok male shoppers. The changed hypothesis of contemplated activity is suitable to clarify male customer conduct in the buy of particular restorative item in the Thai setting.

Purchaser

Consumer Behavior: The Psychology of Marketing

1. The brain research of how customers think, feel, reason, and select between various options (e.g., brands, items, and retailers);
2. The brain science of how the buyer is impacted by his or her surroundings (e.g., society, family, signs, media);
3. The conduct of purchasers while shopping or settling on other showcasing choices;
4. How customer inspiration and choice procedures vary between items that contrast in their level of significance or interest that they involve for the purchaser; and
5. How advertisers can adjust and enhance their promoting effort and showcasing systems to all the more successfully achieve the customer.
6. Behavior happens either for the individual, or with regards to a gathering (e.g., companions impact what sorts of garments a man wears) or an association (individuals at work settle on choices as to which items the firm ought to utilize).

7. Consumer conduct includes the utilization and transfer of items and in addition the investigation of how they are obtained. Item utilize is frequently of awesome enthusiasm to the advertiser, since this may impact how an item is best situated or how we can empower expanded utilization.
8. Consumer conduct includes administrations and thoughts and in addition unmistakable items.
9. The effect of shopper conduct on society is additionally of importance. For instance, forceful advertising of high fat nourishments, or forceful promoting of simple credit, may have genuine repercussions for the national wellbeing and economy.

Table 1: Demographics of consumers

S.no	Characteristics	No of Respondent	Percentage
1. Age	Below 20 years	24	19
	21-30 years	72	58
	31-40 years	20	16
	Above 40 years	9	7
2. Gender	Male	55	44
	Female	70	56
3. Marital status	Married	43	34
	Unmarried	82	66
4. Education	School level	20	16
	Degree/Diploma	30	24
	PG	73	58
	Professional	2	2
5. Occupation	Student	71	57
	Employed	25	20
	Housewife	10	8
	Business	19	15
6. Monthly income	Up to Rs.5,000	24	19
	Rs.5,000 to Rs.10,00	29	23
	Rs.10,000 to s.20,000	40	32
	Above Rs.20,000	32	26
7. Size of the family	Up to 2	11	9
	2 to 4	81	65
	4 to 6	24	19
	Above 6	9	7
8. Modes of Awareness	Advertisement	70	56
	Sample	10	8
	Friends	19	15
	Catalogue	7	6
	Word of mouth	9	7
	Others	10	8

9. Influence of Advertisement	Better Recall	22	18
	Positive Impression	50	40
	Interest	33	26
	Better Exposure	20	16
10. Mode of Payment	Credit card/ Debit card	31	25
	Cash	86	69
	Credit	8	6
11. Attractive Wise Classification of Respondents	Skincare Product	24	19
	Hair Care	26	21
	Detergent Powder	9	7
	Tooth Paste	17	14
	Cool Drinks	23	18
	Edible oil	2	2
12. Preference of Purchase	Dairy Products	24	19
	Department stores	75	60
	Super market	25	20
	Convenient stores	19	15
13. Reasons for Purchase	Krishna stores	6	5
	Discount	26	21
	Service	46	37
	Proximity	8	6
14. Duration of Usage	Ambience	6	5
	Last six months	24	19
	6 months to 1 Year	38	30
	1-2 years	17	14
15. Reason for Usage of Old Brand	More than 2 years	46	37
	Cost	15	12
	Quality	54	43
	Satisfaction	44	35
	More benefit	7	6
	Seasonal change	5	4

Source: Primary Data

58% (72) of the respondents were between the age group of 21-30 years. 56% (70) of the respondents were female. 66% (82) of the respondents were unmarried. 58% (73) of the respondents were PG. 57% (71) of the respondents were students. 32% (40) of the respondents income was between Rs.10,000 to Rs.20,000. 65% (81) of the respondents had 2-4 earning members in the family. 52% (65) of the respondents were having the awareness of FMCG products. 56% (70) of the respondents were come to know about the FMCG through advertisement. 62% (78) of the respondents were purchased the product after the advertisement. 40% (50) of the respondents were influenced by positive impression. 78% (98) of the respondents knew expiry date. 94% (118) of the respondents were checking MRP rate. 77% (96) respondent's opined that FMCG products are

available in rural areas. 69% (86) of the respondents were purchased by cash. 21% (26) of the respondent are using hair care products. 60% (70) of the respondents were preferred department stores. 37% (46) of the respondents were opted for service. 52% (65) of the respondents were choosing branded products. 37% (46) of the respondents were using the product more than 2 years. 84% (100) of the respondents were continuing their old brand. 43% (54) of the respondents were using the product because of quality.

Table No: 2 Problems While Purchasing Fmcg Products

Problems	Rank Weights	I 10	II 9	III 8	IV 7	V 6	VI 5	VII 4	VIII 3	IX 2	X 1	Total score	Rank
Price		100	45	56	161	36	40	88	30	36	16	608	10
Quality		140	90	64	91	120	70	24	38	30	12	679	8
Availability		150	99	120	98	78	30	52	48	14	15	704	6
Lack of awareness about the product		150	90	56	56	84	105	56	52	16	15	680	7
Expired products available		130	99	40	119	96	40	20	30	40	8	622	9
Goodwill of the product		140	90	104	49	108	95	40	78	22	14	740	3
Mode of delivery		90	126	88	105	102	50	52	91	24	9	737	4
Duplication		150	90	152	98	66	25	56	120	18	13	788	1
Less choice		130	45	160	77	90	45	44	99	24	15	729	5
Mode of payment		100	108	112	35	90	65	80	150	12	13	765	2

Source: primary data

Table No-2 Reveals the buying of FMCG items. Issues of duplication secured first rank (788) while method of installment secured (765) second rank. Third issue is goodwill of the item (740) while method of conveyance got forward rank (737). Fifth issue is less decision of the item (729) while accessibility of item is 6th rank (704). Seventh issue is absence of mindfulness about the item (680) while nature of item is eight rank (679). ninth issue is lapsed item are accessible (622) while cost of FMCG items is tenth rank (608).

Table-3 Academic Qualification and mode of Awareness

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant relationship between academic qualification and mode of awareness.

H1: There is significant relationship between academic qualification and mode of awareness.

Table: 3 Analysis Using Correlation

		Academic Qualification	Mode of Awareness
Academic qualification	Pearson Correlation	1	-.191
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.185
	N	50	50
Mode of awareness	Pearson Correlation	-.191	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.185	
	N	50	50

Source: Calculated data

The noteworthy worth (- 0.191) is under 5% of noteworthiness level. So the invalid theory is rejected. Subsequently there is critical relationship between scholarly capability and method of mindfulness.

Table: 4 Occupational Status And Brand Attractiveness

	Occupational Status	Brand Attractiveness
Chi-Square	33.360a	3.600b
Df	3	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.463

Source: calculated value

Chi-square = 3.6, p = 0.463

The significant value (0.463) is less than 5% of significance level. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is significant association between occupation status and brand attraction.

Monthly Income and Duration of Usage

H0: There is no significant relationship between monthly income and duration of usage

H1: There is significant relationship between monthly income and duration of usage

Table: 5 Monthly Income And Duration Of Usage

	Monthly Income	Duration of Usage
Chi-Square	2.160a	5.840a
Df	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.540	.120

Source: calculated value

Chi-square = 2.16, p = 0.54

The critical worth (0.54) is under 5% of noteworthiness level. So the invalid speculation is acknowledged. Subsequently there is no critical relationship between monthly income and term of utilization.

ANOVA Occupational Status and Department Stores

One way ANOVA is a statistical technique that is used to compare the means of more than two groups

Hypothesis

Null hypothesis H0: There is no significant difference between occupational status and customer of particular department stores.

Alternate hypothesis H1: There is significant difference between occupational status and customer of particular department stores.

Table -6 Occupational Status and Customer of Department Stores

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Occupational status	Between Groups	3.421	4	.855	.737	.572
	Within Groups	52.199	45	1.160		
	Total	55.620	49			

Kannan department	Between Groups	26.461	4	6.615	3.339	.018
	Within Groups	89.159	45	1.981		
	Total	115.620	49			
Anantha department	Between Groups	11.619	4	2.905	1.616	.187
	Within Groups	80.881	45	1.797		
	Total	92.500	49			
Reliance fresh	Between Groups	8.758	4		1.064	.386
	Within Groups	92.622	45	2.189		
	Total	101.380	49	2.058		
Valarmathi stores	Between Groups	8.758	4		1.064	.386
	Within Groups	92.622	45	2.189		
	Total	101.380	49	2.058		
Selva department	Between Groups	8.320	4	2.080	1.083	.376
	Within Groups	86.400	45	1.920		
	Total	94.720	49			
SKS department	Between Groups	7.624	4	1.906	1.281	.292
	Within Groups	66.956	45	1.488		
	Total	74.580	49			

Source: calculated value

$F = 0.737, P = 0.572$

Result: Null hypothesis is accepted, because table value is higher than the calculated value. There is no significant difference between occupational status and customer of particular department stores.

Table - 7 Factor Analysis Selected Factors And Ratios With Factor Loading

Factor	Variables	Factor Loading
Factor 1	Reliance fresh	0.578
	Barani department stores	0.698
	Manipal stores	0.579
Factor 2	Sri selvakumar departmental stores	0.776
Factor 3	Valarmathimaligai stores	0.579
	Sri selvakumar departmental stores	0.636
Factor 4	Anantha departmental stores	0.541
Factor 5	Valarmathimaligai stores	0.555
Factor 6	Kovai department stores	0.658

Source: computed data

The selected six factors are interpreted as follows

Factor 1: The opinion with high loading on this factor is concerned with Reliance Fresh, Baranidepartment store, Manipal stores.

Factor 2: The opinion with high loading on this factor is concerned with SRI Selvekumar department stores.

Factor 3: The opinion with high loading on this factor is concerned with Valarmathi Maligai stores, Sri Krishna stores

Factor 4: The opinion with high loading on this factor is concerned with Anatha department stores.

Factor 5: The opinion with high loading on this factor is concerned with Valarmathi Maligai stores.

Factor 6: The opinion with high loading on this factor is concerned with Kovai department stores.

Conclusion

It is finished up from this study FMCG area is developing and will keeps on developing quick. The fates for the FMCG segment look to a great degree empowering. The segment having under gone a basic change is good to go to develop more grounded in future. The FMCG market remains profoundly divided with half of the business sector speaking to mark up bundle hand crafted item. This exhibits a gigantic open door for the business sectors of marked item. The study on the purchaser conduct towards the results of FMCG has gotten a urgent position in the business sector for glue, cleanser, cleanser in spite of the fact that there are numerous rivals in the business sector. FMCG could keep up hold its top rank giving quality item at sensible cost to customer. Quality is the principle inspiring variable for the buyer to purchase the result of FMCG. Presentation of new items in the business sector to fulfill the purchaser is likewise a significance purpose behind FMCGs to hold the top in the shopper market. It clears from the study that FMCG get a noteworthy offer in the shopper merchandise advertise the assembling as to give quality products at sensible cost. The FMCGs division is an exceptionally dynamic part in India. A noteworthy objective is to fulfill the necessities and needs of purchaser and their objective markets all the more adequately and effectively. Thus the specialist trusts that the data gave in this study will help organizations in molding their showcasing methodologies and better serving their clients.

Bibliography

1. Muthuvelayutham (2012) The Study of Consumer Brand Loyalty on FMCG- Cosmetic Products with Special Reference to Madurai. *European Journal of Scientific Research* ISSN 1450-216X, Vol.71, No.1, (2012), pp. 127-143.
2. Chandrasekhar (2012) Consumer Buying Behaviour and Brand Loyalty in Rural Markets: FMCG. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSRJBM)* ISSN: 2278-487X Volume 3, Issue 2 (July-Aug. 2012), pp. 50-67.
3. Suresh Bhagwat (2011) FMCG Markets to contribute in Indian rural Economy perspective in global era. *Half yearly Vision*.
4. Gihan Wijesundera (2010) Factors influencing the demand of beauty soap among female consumers in the greater Colombo region. *ICBI 2010 - University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka*.
5. Nuntasaree Sukat (April 2009) in this article “A model of male consumer behaviour in buying ,skin care products in Thailand. *ABAC Journal* Vol. 29, No. 1 (January-April 2009, pp.39-52).
6. Ankit Katiyar, and Nikha Katiyar, “An Empirical Study of Indian Consumer Buying Behavior of FMCG Products (With Special Reference of Bathing Soap)”, *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations*, Vol. 2, ISSN 2348-7585, Issue 1, 2014, pp.211-217.
7. Chitra.R “An empirical study on Customers Purchase Intention towards Branded Apparels”, *Indian Journal of Research in Management, Business and Social Sciences (IJRMBSS)*, Vol.2, ISSN No: 2319-6998, Issue 1, Jan. 2014, pp.46-49.

8. Nasrudeen. Rand Mohamed, “Level of Consumption of Fast Moving Consumer Goods by Rural Consumers – An Analytical Study”, International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom, Vol.II, Issue 1, ISSN: 2348 0386, 2014, pp.1-21. Rajasekaran, Band Saravanan, P.A. (2014), “Consumer Satisfaction on Fast Moving Consumer Goods”, GJRA-Global Journal for Research Analysis, Vol.2, Issue 8, ISSN No.:2277-8160, August 2014, pp.38-41.
9. Sonia and Garima Dalal, “to Study the Satisfaction Level of Customers towards the Brand of Consumer’s Goods- A Study Carried out on Rural Masses”, GALAXY International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, Vol.2 (4), ISSN 2347-6915, April 2014, pp. 43-52.
<http://www.rediff.com/money/2003/oct/25spec2.html>
www.google.com

Books

1. Consumer Behavior & Marketing Research, Suja R Nair, Himalay Publishing House, 1st. Edition, 2004.
2. Consumer Behavior, ICFAI University, May - 2005.
3. Consumer Behavior, Leon G. Schiffman & Leslie Lazar Karuk, PHI - EEE, 9th. Edition, 1999. Indian Journal of Research in Management, Business and Social Sciences (IJRMBSS), Vol.2, ISSN No. : 2319-6998, Issue 1, Jan. 2014, pp.46-49.
4. Nasrudeen. Rand Mohamed, “Level of Consumption of Fast Moving Consumer Goods by Rural Consumers – An Analytical Study”, International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom, Vol.II, Issue 1, ISSN 2348 0386, 2014, pp. 1-21. Rajasekaran, Band Saravanan, P.A.(2014), “Consumer Satisfaction on Fast Moving Consumer Goods”, GJRA-Global Journal for Research Analysis, Vol. 2, Issue. 8, ISSN No: 2277-8160, August 2014, pp.38-41.
5. Sonia and Garima Dalal, “to Study the Satisfaction Level of Customers towards the Brand of Consumers Goods - A Study Carried out on Rural Masses”, GALAXY International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, Vol.2 (4), ISSN 2347-6915, April 2014, pp. 43-52.
6. <http://www.rediff.com/money/2003/oct/25spec2.html>.
7. www.google.com.

Books

1. Consumer Behavior & Marketing Research, Suja R Nair, Himalay Publishing House, 1st. Edition, 2004.
2. Consumer Behavior, ICFAI University, May - 2005.
3. Consumer Behavior, Leon G. Schiffman & Leslie Lazar Karuk, PHI - EEE, 9th. Edition, 2006.